

1 **Comparison of the energetic stress associated with experimental *Nosema***
2 ***ceranae* and *Nosema apis* infection of honeybees (*Apis mellifera*)**

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12

13 **Abstract**

14 *Nosema ceranae* is a relatively new and widespread parasite of the western
15 honeybee *Apis mellifera* that provokes a new form of nosemosis. In comparison
16 to *Nosema apis*, which has been infecting the honeybee for much longer, *N.*
17 *ceranae* seems to have co-evolved less with this host, causing a more virulent
18 disease. Given that *N. apis* and *N. ceranae* are obligate intracellular microsporidian
19 parasites, needing host energy to reproduce, energetic stress may be an important
20 factor contributing to the increased virulence observed. Through feeding experiments
21 on caged bees, we show that both mortality and sugar syrup consumption were higher
22 in *N. ceranae*-infected bees than in *N. apis*-infected and control bees. The mortality
23 and sugar syrup consumption are also higher in *N. apis*-infected bees than in
24 controls, but are less than in *N. ceranae*-infected bees. With both microsporidia,
25 mortality and sugar syrup consumption increased in function of the increasing spore
26 counts administered for infection. The differences in energetic requirements between
27 both *Nosema* spp. confirm that their metabolic patterns are not the same, which may
28 depend critically on host-parasite interactions and, ultimately, on host pathology. The
29 repercussions of this increased energetic stress may even explain the changes in host
30 behavior due to starvation, lack of thermoregulatory capacity, or higher rates of
31 trophallaxis, which might enhance transmission and bee death.

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34

35 **Introduction**

36 It is obvious that, when a parasite outcompetes its host for the nutrient resources
37 available, the host itself will suffer severe energetic stress. Infected hosts may appear
38 to compensate for such a situation by feeding more, although they also are less
39 efficient in obtaining energy than uninfected hosts. Therefore, not only do parasites
40 take nutrients and energy away from hosts, but they also lower the rate at which
41 energy becomes available for hosts to carry out vital functions (Walkey and Meakins
42 1970). Changes in feeding behavior following infection are just one example of the
43 many potential alterations that might arise due to the need to assimilate more
44 nutrients (Milinski 1985), and indeed, energetic stress typically underlies many of the
45 physiological and behavioral alterations induced by infection (Milinski 1984).

46

47 Microsporidia are spore-forming fungal pathogens that develop as obligate
48 intracellular organisms and infect a wide variety of hosts, ranging from insects to
49 mammals (Adl et al. 2005). As they lack mitochondria and reproduce rapidly within a
50 host cell, taking up ATP from their surroundings, parasitic microsporidia are
51 particularly likely to exert severe energetic stress on their hosts (Williams 2009).
52 *Nosema apis* is a well-studied microsporidian gut parasite that has co-evolved with
53 the western honeybee *Apis mellifera* and is known to cause a series of metabolic
54 changes (Bailey 1981). However, the extent of the energetic stress induced on the
55 honeybee through *N. apis* infection remains unclear. While a decrease in feeding has
56 been observed following the infection of caged bees (Rinderer and Elliot 1977), in
57 another study, food consumption increased with no increase in oxygen consumption,
58 suggesting that the parasite itself is likely to be responsible for producing more hunger
59 rather than the host augmenting its metabolic activity (Moffett and Lawson 1975). By
60 contrast, *Nosema ceranae* is a relatively new microsporidian parasite of *A. mellifera*
61 (Higes et al. 2006; Huang et al. 2007) that was found to cause energetic stress in
62 honeybees, diminishing the survival of infected individuals (Mayack and Naug 2009).
63 By comparison to *N. apis*, *N. ceranae* appears to be more virulent at both the
64 individual and colony levels (Higes et al. 2008; Paxton et al. 2007). This increased
65 virulence could reflect the fact that the parasite–host relationship of *N. ceranae* has
66 evolved over a relatively short period and therefore it exerts more energetic stress on
67 its host. The implications of energetic stress on virulence at the colony level must be
68 taken into consideration since foragers carry a disproportionate parasite load
69 following *N. ceranae* infection (Higes et al. 2008). About 30% of the colonies' energy is
70 spent on foraging, and thus, a decrease in the energy available to individuals in

71 association with the changes in metabolic rate for foraging following infection can
72 strongly affect the energy balance at the colony level and, by consequence, the
73 success of the colony (Harrison and Fewell 2002).

74

75 In recent reviews of *N. ceranae*, the need for more comparative studies of *N. apis* and
76 *N. ceranae* was highlighted in order to distinguish the intrinsic mechanisms
77 associated with the increased virulence observed in infected bees (Paxton 2010; Fries
78 2009). The virulence associated with each parasite–host complex can either
79 drastically increase or decrease over time, and as a result, each must be studied in a
80 case by case manner (May and Anderson 1990). Therefore, feeding experiments on
81 caged bees have been performed to quantify the energetic stress induced by *N. apis*
82 and *N. ceranae* infection. In addition, the mortality of the bees associated with either
83 parasite has been monitored as an indicator of virulence.

84

85 **Methods**

86 **Nosema-free honeybees for experimental infection**

87 Frames of capped brood were obtained from a healthy colony of *Apis mellifera*
88 *iberiensis* (Nosema-free confirmed by PCR) located in an experimental apiary 20 km
89 from the “Centro Apícola”, and they were kept in an incubator at 34°C (±1°C) to
90 provide a supply of newly emerged Nosema-free honeybees. The emergent worker
91 bees were carefully removed, and groups of 25 bees were confined to 40 different
92 cages (175 mm long, 45 mm in diameter) that were kept in the incubator for 5 days.
93 The bees were fed ad libitum with a sucrose solution (50% w/w in distilled water)
94 combined with 2% Promotor L (Calier Lab.), a commercial mixture of amino acids and
95 vitamins. Honey and pollen were not used to feed the bees to avoid possible
96 contamination with infective *Nosema* spp. spores.

97

98 **Production of viable *N. apis* and *N. ceranae* spores**

99 *N. apis* and *N. ceranae* spores were obtained from experimentally infected bees as
100 described previously (Higes et al. 2007). Spores were isolated from adult honeybee
101 samples of naturally infected Spanish honeybee colonies sent to our laboratory for
102 pathological studies. The abdomens of bees were macerated in distilled water (PCR
103 grade) using a sterile manual tissue grinder. The ground contents were filtered through

104 a Whatman mesh (no. 4), and the resulting suspension was re-suspended in distilled
105 water (PCR grade), which was then centrifuged. Each time a pellet of mature spores
106 formed at the bottom of the tube, the liquid at the top was discarded. This procedure
107 was repeated three times to remove all the contaminating debris, and the spores were
108 then quantified using a hemocytometer (OIE 2008), while the *Nosema* species was
109 confirmed by PCR (Martín-Hernández et al. 2007). The spores were divided into
110 batches, stored in distilled water, and they were maintained at a constant
111 temperature until they were used to induce infection.

112

113 Experimental design to determine energy demands and survival

114 Experimental infection was induced in 5-day-old bees as described previously (Higes
115 et al. 2007), and the experimental groups were classified as indicated in Table 1. The
116 concentrations of *N. apis* or *N. ceranae* spores administered were 0, 10³, 10⁴, 5 × 10⁴
117 and 10⁵ spores per bee, and each of the ten groups was established with four
118 replicates of 25 bees in a cage.

119 Before placing the bees in the cages, the bees were starved for 2 h, and then, they
120 were fed individually with 2 µl of 50% sucrose solution containing the appropriate
121 concentration of the inoculum. To achieve the correct dosage, honeybees were
122 anesthetized with CO₂ for ease of handling. When each bee woke up, the droplet of
123 50% sucrose solution mixed with the spores was administered by touching a
124 micropipette to the bee's mouthparts until the entire droplet was consumed. Bees
125 that did not consume the entire droplet were discarded (Malone et al. 1999).
126 Uninfected control bees were fed with 2 µl of the 50% sucrose solution alone.

127

128 After inducing infection, the bees in each cage were fed ad libitum with a sugar syrup
129 made up of 50% sucrose solution with 2% Promotor L (Calier Lab.) through an
130 individual feeder attached to the cage. In order to measure the nutritional demand of
131 infected and uninfected bees, the amount consumed was used as a measure of
132 energetic stress, as described previously (Mayack and Naug 2009). On days 1 (D1), 2
133 (D2), and 6 (D6) post-infection (p.i.), the amount of syrup consumed by each cage of
134 bees was recorded by weighing the feeder, and the mean amount consumed per bee
135 at each time point was then calculated (on the 6th day p.i., the total ingested food was
136 calculated as the daily average consumed food). Two different incubators (Memmert®
137 Mod. IPP500, ±0.1°C) were maintained at 33°C; one contained the *N. ceranae*-

138 infected bees, and the other, *N. apis*-infected bees, in order to avoid cross-
139 contamination. In addition, a group of uninfected bees were kept in each of the two
140 incubators with the infected bees. The cages were observed daily for bee mortality,
141 and all dead bees were removed when detected.

142

143 On the seventh day post-infection, all the remaining living bees were sacrificed by
144 freezing, and the entire abdomen was removed to confirm the *Nosema* species
145 present using the multiplex PCR method described previously (Martín-Hernández et
146 al. 2007). Bees of both control groups served as negative controls and confirmed the
147 absence of infection.

148

149 Statistical analysis

150 A generalized linear model (GLM) was used to study the dependent variables (syrup
151 consumption at three different time points, D1, D2, and D6) and the effects of two
152 fixed factors. These factors included infection at three levels (no infection, infection
153 with *N. apis*, infection with *N. ceranae*), the spore dose administered, and the model
154 used (intercept, infection, and nested spore dose in infection). The differences were
155 calculated to a 95% confidence level with a Wald chi-square test, and the same test
156 was used to estimate the parameters selected to compare the effect between each
157 dose and to calculate the differences between them.

158

159 The data were represented in bar graphs. The differences in syrup consumption on the
160 3 days post-infection were averaged according to the spore doses administered, and
161 then, the differences between the spore doses administered averaged over the 3 days
162 were compared using repeated measures ANOVA with a post hoc Bonferroni analysis.

163

164 Results

165 *N. ceranae*-infected bees consumed significantly more syrup than *N. apis*-infected or
166 uninfected bees throughout the experiment. In infected bees, the amount of syrup
167 consumed increased with the dose of the *N. ceranae* spore inoculum at all the time
168 points analyzed.

169

170 Nutritional demands

171 The overall amount of syrup consumed increased significantly up to day 2 p.i., but it
172 decreased significantly from days 2 to 6 p.i. On days 3, 4, and 5 p.i., the amount of
173 syrup fed to the bees was not recorded as the quantity consumed was negligible. On
174 day 1 p.i. (D1 time point), the fixed factors of the GLM showed an effect of infection on
175 syrup consumption in the bees (Wald chi-square = 480.2; $p < 0.0001$), and on the 2nd
176 day p.i. (D2 time point), the results were similar to those observed on D1. On the 6th
177 day p.i. (D6 time point), only *N. ceranae*-infected bees consumed more syrup than *N.*
178 *apis* and uninfected bees (Wald chi-square = 45.1, $p < 0.0001$; Fig. 1).

179

180 Parasite load

181 As the spore dose increased, there was a significant increase in the amount of syrup
182 consumed by infected bees (Wald chi-square = 152.3; $p < 0.0001$). At all spore doses,
183 *N. ceranae*-infected bees consumed significantly more syrup than *N. apis*-infected or
184 uninfected bees, and *N. apis*-infected bees consumed more syrup than uninfected
185 ones. Considering the combined effects in *N. ceranae*-infected bees (*Nosema*
186 infection and spore dose), the highest amount of syrup consumption was recorded in
187 bees infected with the largest dose of spores, and a dose of 105 spores per bee was
188 the only dose that produced significantly higher consumption than the rest of the
189 spore doses assayed (Wald chi-square = 104.7, $p < 0.0001$). The same was true for *N.*
190 *apis* infection except that the highest amount of spores administered was not
191 significantly different from the rest (Wald chi-square = 22.6, $p < 0.0001$; Fig. 2).

192

193 Bee mortality

194 Honeybee mortality was assessed at different time points during the experiment
195 (Table 2), and no mortality was observed until day 6 p.i. in some of the infected
196 groups. The mortality rates of infected bees showed a similar pattern to their overall
197 energetic demands and the corresponding *Nosema* spore doses. Not only did bees
198 infected with the higher doses of *N. apis* spores suffer higher mortality, but even
199 greater mortality was seen in those infected with *N. ceranae* spores. As such, the
200 highest mortality was evident in the bee group infected with the largest dose of *N.*
201 *ceranae* spores (105 spores/bee), which produced 60.7% of death among the bees 6
202 days p.i. Indeed, mortality reached 93.1% after 7 days p.i. in this group of bees, at
203 which time the mortality was higher in all *N. ceranae*-infected groups than in the

204 control groups. In the case of *N. apis* infection, only the higher doses of spores (105
205 and 5×10^4 spores/bee) produced more mortality than in the control group of bees.

206

207 **Discussion**

208 These results presented here clearly show that *N. ceranae* imposes greater energetic
209 stress on infected bees, suggestive of a stronger virulence in comparison to *N. apis*.
210 Energetic stress is related to the increasing doses of spores for infection, and it is
211 highest in *N. ceranae*-infected bees, which also suffer the worst survival.
212 Furthermore, these data are consistent with previous studies that demonstrate the
213 detrimental effects of *N. ceranae* on individual bees and on colony survival as a whole
214 (Higes et al. 2008; Mayack and Naug 2009; Naug and Gibbs 2009; Alaux et al. 2010).
215 Energetic stress imposed by *N. ceranae* is much more substantial than previously
216 thought, and it persists for much longer, lasting for up to 6 days post-infection.

217 The severe energetic stress observed in *Nosema*-infected bees is probably due to the
218 parasite itself competing directly with its host for key nutrients and energy resources,
219 like most microsporidian species. *N. ceranae* and *N. apis* only develop when in direct
220 contact with the host cell cytoplasm (Fries et al. 1996; De Graaf et al. 1994; Weidner
221 et al. 1999; Higes et al. 2007; Chen et al. 2009a), indicating that the parasite may
222 require some external energy supply to reproduce (Weidner et al. 1999). Microsporidia
223 lack mitochondria, and they have long been suspected to either take up ATP from the
224 host cell environment or gain ATP by metabolizing host cell carbohydrates through the
225 glycolytic pathway (Weidner et al. 1999). Consistent with this notion of ATP uptake,
226 microsporidia have frequently been seen to be surrounded by host mitochondria,
227 which probably facilitate the uptake of ATP from host cells (Dufort et al. 1987;
228 Sokolova et al. 1988; Williams 2009).

229 In these experiments, the parasite dependence on host energy is manifested by the
230 increase in syrup consumption by infected bees, as seen in earlier studies (Mayack
231 and Naug 2009; Alaux et al. 2010). However, it is interesting to note that we found
232 significantly higher feeding in *N. ceranae*-infected bees than in *N. apis*-infected bees.
233 Some years ago, it was found that heavily infected cells of the gut lining may either be
234 dead or dying, provoking poor nutrient absorption in the midgut of the bee and
235 eventually leading to the early death of bees due to starvation (Liu 1984). Intriguingly,
236 there was no difference in virulence between *N. apis*- and *N. ceranae*-infected bees
237 fed ad libitum when administered the same doses of spores as in this experiment
238 (Forsgren and Fries 2010) probably due to differences in the method of infection in the

239 laboratory (e.g., house adult worker bees obtained from combs versus newborn bees
240 obtained in an incubator, etc.). Therefore, the stronger virulence (mortality) of *N.*
241 *ceranae*-infected bees at the same parasite load as *N. apis* is probably due to the
242 severe energetic stress caused by the increased lack of nutrient absorption, which is
243 likely to be due to more aggressive destruction of the gut lining. As a matter of fact, the
244 degeneration of epithelial ventricular cells of the gut lining is more severe in *N.*
245 *ceranae*-infected bees than in *N. apis*-infected bees, diminishing nutrient absorption
246 (Higes et al. 2007) The more aggressive damage to the gut lining in *N. ceranae*-
247 infected caged worker bees has also been detected in naturally infected worker and
248 queen bees (Higes et al. 2008; 2009a, b).

249 Malnutrition that results in a higher within-host parasite load does not necessarily
250 suppress immunocompetence that leads to a higher number of infected individuals in
251 the population, as seen with microsporidia infecting vertebrate hosts (reviewed by
252 Wakelin 1989 and Lloyd 1995). Invertebrate generation times are much shorter than
253 those of vertebrates, and infection of invertebrates is usually chronic. Invertebrate
254 parasites depend strongly on host resources (Pulkkinen and Ebert 2004), and thus, in
255 some instances, severe starvation limits the growth of the parasite within invertebrate
256 hosts. Indeed, severe energetic stress was shown to impede parasite spread and the
257 decrease of the number of infected individuals at a population level
258 when *Daphnia* was infected with the microsporidian *Glugoides intestinalis* (Pulkkinen
259 and Ebert 2004). However, this does not appear to be the case in this study, where
260 consuming significantly more syrup over the period tested probably yields enough
261 additional energy to support the reproduction and larger parasite load of *N. ceranae*-
262 infected bees (Chen et al. 2009b).

263 The severe energetic stress caused by *N. ceranae* when compared with *N. apis* may
264 be related to the immune suppression seen in infected bees. Indeed, there is a clear
265 trade-off between energy acquisition and activation of the insect's immune system to
266 fight infections (Schmid-Hempel 2005). Short-term food deprivation in insects leads
267 to a downregulation of the immune system, resulting in less resistance when
268 challenged with infection. When fed under ideal conditions, the immune system is
269 restored, demonstrating the energetic cost associated with maintaining an effective
270 immune system (Siva-Jothy and Thompson 2002; Feder et al. 1997). In contrast to the
271 activation of the immune system by *N. apis*, *N. ceranae* causes immune suppression
272 (Antúnez et al. 2009), much like the *Varroa* mite that induces energetic stress and
273 facilitates multiple co-infections in honeybees (Gregory et al. 2005; Yang and Cox-
274 Foster 2005).

275 It is important to note that energetic stress was observed in infected bees maintained
276 under ideal laboratory conditions, while under natural conditions, a combination of
277 other factors may represent additional negative influences on honeybees. For
278 example, at sub-lethal levels, pesticides like neonicotinoids have been shown to
279 cause a further increase in energetic stress in *N. ceranae*-infected honeybees (Alaux
280 et al. 2010). Energetic stress has important implications for the success of bee
281 foraging since carbohydrates are their main source of fuel for flight, and foraging is a
282 metabolically expensive activity (Rothe and Nachtigall 1989). Moreover, energetic
283 stress is suspected to be the cause of the poor thermoregulation in infected foragers
284 when they are chilled, and infected bees seek warmer locations within the hive to
285 compensate when they feel cold. This deficient thermoregulation increases the
286 probability of foragers suffering hypothermia, leading to their incapacity to sustain
287 flight and provoking forager starvation outside of the colony (Campbell et al. 2010).
288 Indeed, free-flying foragers infected with *N. ceranae* have lower hemolymph trehalose
289 levels due to energetic stress, and based on the differences in sugar levels, it would
290 be predicted that infected foragers could only fly two thirds the distance of an
291 uninfected forager (Mayack and Naug 2010). The fact that the pollinators' habitat is
292 declining adds yet further stress on honeybee foragers, causing an increase in the
293 distance a honeybee forager has to fly to collect nectar and pollen for the colony
294 (Naug 2009).

295 Not only would *N. ceranae* infection have some individual behavioral effects on
296 foragers, but the colony could also be affected. Increased hunger due to *N.*
297 *ceranae* infection leads to differences in trophallaxis rates within the colony, which
298 may increase the rate of transmission and the spread of the disease (Feigenbaum and
299 Naug 2010; Naug and Gibbs 2009). An increase in an individual's hunger through
300 infection may increase the overall rate of foraging in the colony, as well as the colony's
301 energetic demand regulating foraging. Indeed, hunger at the level of individual
302 foragers within the colony increases foraging rates (Howard and Tschinkel 1980; Toth
303 et al. 2005). Moreover, it is probable that vitellogenin levels can be indirectly
304 modulated by nutritional stress, thereby inducing infected bees to start foraging
305 earlier (Amdam and Omholt 2003; Nelson et al. 2007). The probability of infected
306 foragers starving to death would also increase as they might be unable to fly back to
307 the hive due to energetic stress (Mayack and Naug 2009; Naug 2009). As such,
308 starvation may contribute to colony depopulation, highly infected foragers having
309 been found dead far from their hives (Higes et al. 2008).

310

311 **Conclusion**

312 This study contributes to the growing body of literature demonstrating that *N.*
313 *ceranae* is more virulent than *N. apis* (reviewed in Higes et al. 2010). The increased
314 virulence associated with the energetic stress observed could be due to the shorter
315 co-evolution of the *N. ceranae* parasite–host complex, given that this is a relatively
316 new parasite of the western honeybee when compared to *N. apis* (Higes et al. 2006;
317 Klee et al. 2007). As described here and elsewhere, *N. ceranae* has a relatively
318 important influence in terms of the fitness of its host, both alone or in combination
319 with other agents. *N. ceranae* is probably less efficient in terms of the physiological
320 integration of the host–parasite complex, and it must draw more food from its host
321 due to less efficient energy conversion. Therefore, it is plausible that the stronger
322 virulence observed following *N. ceranae* infection is due to additional energetic stress
323 imposed by this relatively new parasite, over and above that of *N. apis*. Individual
324 energetic stress from infection may have more far-reaching effects in honeybees as
325 they are social insects, affecting the regulation of foraging or immune function, which
326 may potentially affect the survival of infected bees.

327

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495 **Table 1.** The various amounts of spore doses administered at the beginning of the
 496 experiment for *N. apis* and *N. ceranae* species of parasite

Spore dose (spores/bee)	Group name	
	<i>N. apis</i>	<i>N. ceranae</i>
0	A1	C1
10 ³	A2	C2
10 ⁴	A3	C3
5 × 10 ⁴	A4	C4
10 ⁵	A5	C5

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500 **Table 2.** Mortality (mean ± standard deviation) of infected and control groups

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Group	<i>Nosema</i> spp.	Spore dose	Days			
			1 day	2 days	6 days	7 days
			Mortality (%)			
A1	Uninfected	0	0	0	0	4.8 ± 0.9
A2	<i>N. apis</i>	10 ³	0	0	0	4.9 ± 1.1
A3	<i>N. apis</i>	10 ⁴	0	0	0	5.2 ± 0.8
A4	<i>N. apis</i>	5 × 10 ⁴	0	0	10.6 ± 2.7	21.6 ± 1.7
A5	<i>N. apis</i>	10 ⁵	0	0	17.9 ± 2.1	31 ± 0.9
C1	Uninfected	0	0	0	0	4.1 ± 1.1
C2	<i>N. ceranae</i>	10 ³	0	0	0	11.1 ± 2.1
C3	<i>N. ceranae</i>	10 ⁴	0	0	8.4 ± 1.8	20.1 ± 0.9
C4	<i>N. ceranae</i>	5 × 10 ⁴	0	0	22.6 ± 1.2	67.4 ± 1.3
C5	<i>N. ceranae</i>	10 ⁵	0	0	60.7 ± 3.6	93.1 ± 1.6

502 The mortality was calculated as the percentage of the caged bees dead at each
 503 time point

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509 **Figure 1.** The amount of syrup consumed on the 3 days post-infection (days 1, 2,
 510 and 6 p.i.) by *N. apis* ($N = 16$; 4 replicates \times 4 spore doses for each day; *striped bars*) and *N. ceranae* ($N = 16$; 4 replicates \times 4 spore doses for each day; *solid bars*)
 511 compared to their respective control group ($N = 4$; 4 replicates for day
 512 and *Nosema* species; *clear bars*). For clarity, the infected data are pooled across
 513 the 1,000–100,000 spore parasite loads administered at the beginning of the
 514 experiment. The data represent the mean values for each group, and
 515 their *standard deviation bars* and the *multiple asterisks* indicate highly significant
 516 differences between means tested at the 0.05 alpha level.
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531 **Figure 2.** The amount of syrup consumed by bees infected with *N. apis* ($N = 12$; 4
 532 replicates \times 3 days for spore dose; *striped bars*), *N. ceranae* ($N = 12$; 4
 533 replicates \times 3 days for spore dose; *solid bars*), and their respective controls
 534 ($N = 12$; 4 replicates \times 3 days; *clear bars*), plotted as a function of the 1,000–
 535 100,000 parasite load administered at the beginning of the experiment. For clarity,
 536 the infected data are pooled across the three measurements post-infection. The
 537 data represent the mean values for each group with the *standard deviation*
 538 *bars* and *letters* indicating significant differences between means at the 0.05 alpha
 539 level

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